

Studies on 3-Aminocoumarin Derivatives as Potent Antifungal and Antibacterial Agents

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A series of eighteen (3d-u) different thiobarbituric acid derivatives of 3-aminocoumarin were synthesised. All the compounds have been screened for antifungal and antibacterial activities. The structure of the compounds have been established by their elemental analysis, ir, nmr and mass spectra data.

HETEROCYCLIC compounds are well-known in the field of pesticidal chemistry. Five- or six-membered ring with hetero atom, such as oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur impart special biological activity¹ to the compounds. In the development of pesticidal chemistry it has been seen that a great number of pesticides are characterised by the presence of carbonyl group adjacent to an ether linkage or a lactone ring². Coumarin is the best known lactone³ of the aromatic group. Coumarins possess various biological activities⁴. Barbituric acid as well as thiobarbituric acids are well-known biological agents⁵. The replacement of the basic N⁴ amino group of sulphonamides by such groups as aryl amino and azo effects bacteriostatic action⁶ due to *in vivo* release of the parent sulphonamide by metabolic processes.

Thus in view of the reported biological activities of 3-aminocoumarins⁷ it was thought of interest to undertake the synthesis of a series of compounds in which the coumarin moiety was incorporated with the thiobarbiturates at 3-position of the coumarin system.

The present communication describes the synthesis of thiobarbituric acid derivatives of 3-aminocoumarins and their pesticidal activity. The condensation of 3-aminocoumarin with different substituted aryl isothiocyanates *N*-aryl-2-(coumarin-3-yl)aminocarbothiamide (1). Ir spectra of 3-aminocoumarin showed band at 1720 (C=O lactone ring) and 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH₂); the disappearance of NH₂ band and the presence of 3310 (NH) and 1240 cm⁻¹ (C=S) bands confirms the formation of 1. These aminocarbothiamides were cyclised with the help of malonic acid in presence of acetyl chloride to give different substituted-thiobarbituric acids (2a-c). Disappearance of NH band in the ir spectra of 2 showed its formation. These were further made to undergo Japp-Klingmann reaction with different substituted-benzenesulphonamides, primary amines, substituted-oxadiazoles and thiadiazoles to give the title compounds (3d-u). It was

confirmed by the presence of ir bands (3d) at 1620-1625 (N=N) and 3003 cm⁻¹ (C-H).

Biological activities: The compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Chaetomium globosum*, *Fusarium culmorum*, *Pullularia pullulans* and *Trichoderma viride*, using solution of the compound in 5% DMF in acetone by agar plate diffusion

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R'	R''	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula/ (Mol. wt.)
2a	H		70	145	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂ S (864)
2b	Cl		65	115	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ SOCl (898)
2c	OH ₂		71	205	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S (878)
3d	H	4,6-Dimethyl- pyrimidino	75	161	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂ (658)
3e	H	Pyrimidino	70	153	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂ (625)
3f	H	Guanidino	72	188	C ₂₆ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₇ S ₂ (589)
3g	H	<i>p</i> -Br-Aniline	60	122	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ SBr (559)
3h	H	4-Methyl- thiadiazole	50	158	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂ (490)
3i	H	4- <i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl- oxadiazole	50	170	C ₂₇ H ₁₅ O ₆ N ₆ SOCl (570)
3j	Cl	4,6-Dimethyl- pyrimidino	70	175	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₆ H ₇ S ₂ Cl (687)
3k	Cl	Pyrimidino	71	162	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₇ S ₂ Cl (660)
3l	Cl	Guanidino	74	138	C ₂₆ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₇ S ₂ Cl (624)
3m	Cl	<i>p</i> -Br-Aniline	61	147	C ₂₆ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄ SBrCl (549)
3n	Cl	4-Methylthia- diazole	45	172	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂ Cl (525)
3o	Cl	4- <i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl- oxadiazole	42	140	C ₂₇ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₆ SOCl ₂ (605)
3p	OH ₂	4,6-Dimethyl- pyrimidino	66	162	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₇ S ₂ (667)
3q	OH ₂	Pyrimidino	69	142	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₇ S ₂ (639)
3r	OH ₂	Guanidino	70	148	C ₂₇ H ₃₁ O ₆ N ₇ S ₂ (603)
3s	OH ₂	<i>p</i> -Br-Aniline	55	133	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₄ SBr (561)
3t	OH ₂	4-Methyl- thiadiazole	45	124	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ S (472)
3u	OH ₂	4- <i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl- oxadiazole	40	155	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₆ SOCl (584)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

technique⁸. All the fungal cultures were maintained on Sobourand's agar slant⁹.

Most of the screened compounds showed 70% inhibition at the concentration of 500 ppm. 3g, 3h and 3m showed more than 70% inhibition at the lower concentration (250 ppm). In view of the structure-activity relationship the appreciable activity was exhibited by compounds having *p*-Br substitution in arylazo moiety, i.e. 3g, 3m, and most of the compounds having *p*-CH₃ substitution in the 3-substituted-aryl moiety showed inhibition against fungi. While *p*-Cl compounds were not much active.

Antibacterial activity was determined by following the agar-diffusion technique¹⁰ against *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Among 14 of the 18 compounds tested for bactericidal activity, most of them were found to be inactive. Compounds 3g, 3m and 3n showed 75% activity at 500 ppm concentration level; 3m also

showed such activity at 250 ppm level. It was found that compounds having *p*-Br substitution in the arylazo moiety showed remarkable activity against the bacteria.

Experimental

Melting points were uncorrected and determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Tlc was performed on silica gel G plates using iodine vapour as visualising agent.

3-Aminocoumarin: It was prepared by the literature method¹¹.

N-Aryl-2-(coumarin-3-yl)aminocarbothiamide (1): To a solution of 3-aminocoumarin (0.01 mol) in ethanol was added equimolar amount (0.01 mol) of substituted phenyl isothiocyanate and the mixture

was refluxed for 6 h. The resulting solid was washed with cold ethanol and crystallised from ethanol to give **1a-c** as shining needles (80%): **1a** m.p. 180° (Found: C, 64.80; H, 4.10; N, 9.31. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4N_2S$ requires: C, 64.86; H, 4.05; N, 9.46%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 310 (NH), 1 700 (C=O lactonic), 1 560 (NH bending), 1 240 (C=S), 1 120 (C-N) and 2 950 cm^{-1} (CH or CH_2).

1-(Coumarin-3-yl)-3-substituted-aryl-2-thiobarbituric acid (2a-c): A mixture of **1a** (0.01 mol) and malonic acid (0.15 mol) in acetyl chloride (7 ml) was condensed on a water-bath at 40–50%. The solution was then poured over crushed ice with stirring. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol and chloroform to give **2a** as orange solid (70%), m.p. 145° (Found: C, 62.10; H, 3.50; N, 7.61. $C_{19}H_{12}O_4N_2S$ requires: C, 62.06; H, 3.58; N, 7.69%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 200 (C=S), 3 015 (CH or CH_2) and 1 730 cm^{-1} (C=O lactone).

Other compounds (**2b-c**) were synthesised in the same manner (Table 1).

1-(Coumarin-3-yl)-3-substituted-phenyl-5-aryldiazothio-barbituric acid (3d-u): Appropriate aromatic amines (0.01 mol) were taken in HCl-acetic acid (4:3) and cooled below -5° in freezing mixture. Cold aqueous $NaNO_2$ solution (0.15 mol) was simultaneously added to the cold solution of the amine to undergo diazotisation. The diazonium salt was added to the cold solution of **2** in pyridine with vigorous stirring. The resulting solution was left in freezing mixture for 1 h and then left overnight at room temperature. It was then poured over crushed ice. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol and chloroform to give crystals of **3d** (75%), m.p. 161° (Found: C, 56.62; H, 3.16; N, 14.95. $C_{23}H_{20}O_6N_7S_2$ requires: C, 56.96; H, 3.52; N, 15.00%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 620–1 625 (N=N), 1 200 (C=S), 3 003 (CH), 1 720 (C=O lactonic) and 1 310–1 150 cm^{-1} (two bands; SO_2 stretch); $\delta(CDCl_3 + DMSO-d_6)$ 2.68 (1H, s, O=C-CH-C=O), 2.35

(3H, s, $H_2N-C=NH$), 6.8–8.0 (13H, m, ArH and CH of lactonic ring) and 8.65 (1H, sb, SO_2NH).

Similarly, other compounds (**3e-u**) were synthesised (Table 1).

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References

1. A. I. VIRTONEAN and P. K. HIETALA, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1960, **14**, 499; P. C. JOSHI and P. C. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 467.
2. LAUGER, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1944, **27**, 892.
3. A. A. ELLINGER, *Arch. Pathol. Pharmacol. Suppl.*, 1908, 150.
4. E. FRANZ, E. KLAUBO and I. HAMMANN, Ger. Pat. 3 012 642/1981 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1982, **96**, 14276), Y. D. REDDY and V. V. SOMAYAYULU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 599, R. H. BOURGAIN, R. V. ORIESSCHE and P. SMITH, *Arch. Inst. Pharmacodyn. Ther.*, 1972, **195**, 240; B. R. MOFFELT, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, **7**, 446, A. K. RAO, M. S. RAJU and K. M. RAJU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 1021.
5. "Goodman and Gilman's The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", 5th. ed., Macmillan, New York, pp. 354-375; I. FEINBERG, G. FEIN and J. M. WALKER, *Science*, 1977, **198**, 847.
6. L. E. ROTTIGER and H. MOLLERBERG, *Acta Med. Scand.*, 1959, **165**, 241; E. E. SMISSMAN, "Textbook of Organic Medicinal Chemistry", 6th. ed., Lippincott, 1971, p. 285.
7. P. L. FAZZI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1959, **53**, 14213.
8. J. C. MARSHFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1954, **5**, 652.
9. F. CAVANAGH, *Anal. Microbiol.*, 1963, 126.
10. R. S. VERMA and S. A. IMAM, *Ind. J. Microbiol.*, 1979, **13**, 45.
11. W. F. LINCHE, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 28, 280, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 1758; K. C. PANDYA, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1939, **8**, 173, *Curr. Sci.*, 1939, **8**, 203.